

EXPERIENCES OF STUDENT EXCHANGE IN FINLAND - HOW TO PREPARE UZBEK UNIVERSITY STUDENTS FOR EXCHANGE STUDIES IN FINLAND?

Johanna Järveläinen

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10156514>

Abstract. *Student mobility is an integral part of the university studies of an increasing number of young people. This article discusses the experiences of Uzbek university student during his higher education studies in Finland. The article highlights the main cultural differences identified by the student and suggests ways to take cultural aspects into account in Finnish language teaching in the home country in order to prepare the future students for their exchange studies in Finland.*

Keywords: *cultural differences, culturally oriented language teaching, student exchange, Finnish language*

Introduction

In our globalised world, more and more young people are planning to study abroad or at least to include a student exchange in their studies. Nordic International University in Tashkent, Uzbekistan, offers its students the opportunity to do a double degree with the Finnish Karelia University of Applied Sciences in international business, industrial management and information and communication technology. Nordic International University is a new, private university established in 2022, so the first exchange students are preparing to leave in autumn 2024.

The three fields of study also include 12-16 credits of Finnish language teaching, the amount depending on the field. Language and culture often go hand in hand, but for these students the need for culturally focused language teaching is even more obvious: in order to adapt to their new country of study and its culture, students need to know about the topic in advance. But what should students be told? What should they know about their host country to help them adapt to the demands of their new environment and their studies? This article aims to answer these questions and to show how to implement culturally focused Finnish language teaching for groups going on student exchange.

Materials and Methods

Teaching Finnish as a second/foreign language often involves not only language but also culture. The teacher highlights what he or she considers to be essential aspects of the culture, such as customs, festivals and traditions, also taking into account the needs of the group he or she is teaching. However, for example for the author of this article, as a Finnish teacher of Finnish, her perspective on Finnish culture is different from what it would be to someone from a different cultural background. In this article, the focus of interest is especially on what in Finnish culture amazes and surprises a university student from Uzbekistan.

As mentioned, Nordic International University is a new university, so students from there have not yet gone on university exchange. However, the exchange has been possible from Kokand University. For this article, one of the exchange students from Kokand in Finnish Karelia University of Applied Sciences was interviewed. He has now been studying in Finland almost two years. The interview was conducted in written form on Telegram, as the student was in Finland at the time of it. The interview form contained open questions, so the student was able to raise cultural issues that he considered important. The author of this article was also able to ask more specific questions about the themes of the interview, if necessary.

With such a small sample size, the results are not widely generalisable. However, they do give an indication of what aspects should be included in culturally focused Finnish language teaching, especially from the perspective of exchange students from Uzbekistan.

Detecting Cultural Differences

Ward, Bochner and Furnham (2005, 7) note that anthropologist Kalervo Oberg (1960) defined the process of adaptation to a new culture and environment as a culture shock, which has four stages. The first is the honeymoon period, when the new culture seems fascinating and attractive. This phase is followed by a crisis, with a range of emotions including frustration and fear, even anger. The third phase is the recovery, where the crisis is overcome and the new culture is learned from. The final or fourth stage is adjustment, where the person is already able to function and thrive in the new environment. (Ward, Bochner & Furnham 2005, 84.) Later, also many other models have been proposed to describe culture shock, but Oberg's definition is still widely used, for example in materials for international students at various universities (see e.g., University of Helsinki).

The university student interviewed does not use the word 'culture shock' to describe his experiences, but states that he encountered a notable cultural adjustment. As an example of this, he highlights the Finns' need for personal space:

While waiting at bus stops in Finland, I made an observation that typically, 2-3 individuals maintained a distance of approximately 4-5 meters from each other as they awaited the same bus. Subsequently, I began to contemplate that this practice reflected a cultural preference among Finnish people for personal space.

The student's attention to the Finns waiting for the bus far away from each other reflects not only the personal space, but also the fact that so-called small talk is not natural for Finns. People who do not know each other do not necessarily start talking, even if they are all involved in the same situation, waiting for the bus. The student comments that her friends have experienced sometimes the differences in norms might make the Finnish behaviour to feel even rude or impolite.

The student says also that it is noteworthy to mention, on certain occasions, he observed Finns being shy in communicating in English. The Finnish education system guarantees that everyone born since 1970's has learned English at school. However, even though Finnish people have the language skills, this doesn't mean that it is easy for them to participate in a discussion on foreign language, which the student was also able to observe. A stereotype of a Finn is a shy person, and even if the stereotypes are not the whole truth and can be even harmful, they have sometimes the power to describe characteristics shared by the same nationality with astonishing accuracy.

The Finnish climate has also caused the student some problems. Finland has four seasons, but the difference in light levels between summer and winter is significant. The student describes his experiences as follows:

To tell the truth, Finland's climate is distinctive, characterized by extended summer days with prolonged daylight, and very dark periods in the winter. From my personal experience, during the summer, there were exceptionally lengthy days, spanning a duration of approximately 14-15 hours, which occasionally disrupted my sleep due to the presence of daylight persisting throughout the late evening.

However, the student has clearly found ways with other exchange students to help them adapt to a climate that is different from their own, and does not see it as an insurmountable obstacle to their enjoyment:

When we first moved, we were a little concerned about the darker winter months, but all you have to do is keep yourself busy and the winters are fun. Every week we usually participated in downhill skiing, cross-country skiing, snowmobiling, sledging or ice-skating. Among the activities I found most appealing was skiing at the Mustavaara ski center, located approximately thirty minutes away from the heart of Joensuu. This marked my inaugural experience skiing in this location, and it constituted a truly indelible moment in my life.

According to the interviewed student, it is possible that the things one is the most afraid of adapting to in advance turn out to be opportunities for enjoyable new experiences.

Observations on Educational Culture

In Finland the digitalisation process has been quick, which also shows in the field of education. In Finnish universities, a lot of different educational tools and information systems are used, which also the interviewed student noticed immediately:

At the beginning of my academic year, the primary problem I encountered involved acquiring proficiency in the utilization of various platforms, including but not limited to Moodle, Peppi, TUUDO, and the Outlook email system. Notably, the use of email was a novel experience for me, as it had not been a part of my academic routine at Kokand University. My transition to Karelia UAS necessitated the acquisition of this skill, which involved learning the conventions of effective email communication.

Moodle is a learning management system, where the teacher can upload all the information needed during the course: the schedule, assessment criteria and materials needed. The student can also return their assignments to Moodle. Peppi is a learning information system, where a student can sign into the courses, see his grades of the courses and follow his weekly schedule. Teachers mark the grades to Peppi, as well as use it e.g. to get the student lists for different teaching groups. TOODO is a bit like Peppi, but in a form of an application. It includes information on student’s everyday studies. It is worth in the beginning of an exchange to spend the time for learning the use of these environments, in order to be able to study effectively. The universities in Finland usually have orientation week where the use of the different systems is taught. They also tend to have an effective helpdesk, which answers quickly about any technical problems encountered.

Telegram is not widely used in Finland, and many people use WhatsApp instead. However, especially the official information is never delivered via WhatsApp or Telegram, but as the student mentions, by e-mail. In the context of higher education, e-mail is used student-teacher communication, as well as for delivering information to a certain group of students. In general, in working life, the tool of communication is also the e-mail.

The student has been studying in Finland just after the pandemic, so he has experienced also the distance teaching:

As a notable example, in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic in KU (Kokand University), a complete shift to offline teaching was instituted, whereas at Karelia UAS, it has come to my attention that certain courses continue to be conducted in a remote format.

In Finland ‘the digital jump’ was done due the pandemic very quickly. The educational institutions had the tools for distant teaching, but they were not widely in use. The pandemic forced the teachers to shift to online teaching in a short notice. The possibilities of online teaching were

widely acknowledged, and it became a more common form of studying, even after the pandemic years. However, the online studies require the student to have a working computer and reliable internet access. As an advice for the students planning to study in Finland, the interviewed students suggests the following: - - *have access to up-to-date, high-quality computing equipment, including a reliable laptop and smartphone, as these tools play a pivotal role in facilitating their academic endeavors.*

The student has also made general observations on differences in educational cultures:

Certainly, I observed several distinctions in instructional methodologies, the roles of educators, and the expectations of students when comparing the educational systems of Kokand University and Karelia UAS. Moreover, a divergence in the role of educators has become evident to me. I have noticed that, at Karelia UAS, there exists a greater degree of openness in the communication between professors and students, thereby affording students the opportunity to freely pose questions during instructional sessions. In contrast, my experience in KU has indicated that some professors prefer inquiries to be directed to them solely upon the conclusion of the lecture.

In general, Finnish lecturers don't mind the questions of the students and they are not seen as interruptions, but as an active participation to a learning process. Teaching is seen as a dialogical process, where the students are allowed and even encouraged to give and justify their opinions. It is understood that when learning critical thinking, the process includes questioning.

The Importance of Language Skills

The interviewed student had studied Finnish prior to his at Kokand University, which he founds very usefull. Also, a good command of English is a necessity, because International Business program at Karelia University of Applied Sciences is taught in English:

To my mind, students desiring enrollment at Karelia UAS are expected to demonstrate proficiency in the English language. Furthermore, it is advantageous for prospective students to possess a foundational understanding of the Finnish language before arriving in Finland, as this facilitates a more expedient adjustment to the local Finnish environment, particularly considering that certain Finnish residents may have limited English language capabilities

The student sees the language a way for understanding the culture. Not all of the Finnish people feel comfortable by speaking English. He mentions, that he is making an effort to use Finnish language at work as well as with friends, even though he still feels that he doesn't yet have skills for completely fluent communication. However, the learning process is going on.

Reasons to Study in Finland

The student started his studies in Karelia UAS as a part of the exchange programme, which duration for was one year. However, after the completion of the initial exchange programme he and his friend decided to continue their studies in Finland:

[We] made a deliberate decision to extend our academic journey in Finland and transitioned our academic pursuits from Kokand University to Karelia University of Applied Sciences. Commencing from the spring semester of 2023, we enrolled as students in the Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) degree program at Karelia UAS.

It is interesting, how he describes his studies as 'an academic journey'. A journey usually has a beginning, a middle part and the end, but it also includes the idea of being on the move and encountering new, unknown things. Thus, the metaphor suits well to describe the studying in a foreign cultural environment.

The student also gives several reasons, why he felt studying in Finland is a good opportunity for him and his future carrier:

I wanted to study - - in Finland for several valid reasons. One of the primary motivations for selecting this major was the dynamic and ever-expanding nature of international business. The world is becoming increasingly interconnected, and I believe that understanding the intricacies of international trade, finance, and management is essential in today's global economy. International Business program at Karelia University of Applied Sciences offered a comprehensive curriculum that covered a wide range of topics, from cross-cultural communication to global marketing strategies, providing me with a well-rounded education in this field. Furthermore, Finland is known for its exemplary education system, consistently ranking among the top in the world. This, combined with Karelia UAS reputation for delivering high-quality, practical education, made it an ideal place to pursue my BBA degree. The university's focus on real-world experience, internships, and project-based learning meant that I could apply what I was learning in the classroom directly to practical scenarios.

The student’s answer indicates, that he has been thinking the choice of his studies profoundly. He also shows a strong inner motivation for studying abroad and especially in Finland, by making a choice to continue his studies in Finland also after the end of the exchange programme.

Intercultural Competence Includes Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes

International exchange students' experiences of studying abroad and the problems they encounter should be approached through practical encounters, not assumptions (Eze Ogonnia 2015, 50). It should also be remembered that students' experiences of adapting to a new culture are personal. An individual's personal characteristics and background can influence whether studying abroad feels challenging or attractive.

Intercultural competence is considered to be made up of knowledge, skills and attitudes, and is often context-specific. In addition, language skills are needed for effective interaction. (Lasonen, Halonen, Pini Kemppainen & Teräs 2009, 14-15.) The student interviewed in this article seem to have adapted to studying in his new host country well and he seems to have a high degree of intercultural competence. He had a fluent command of English and some basic Finnish language skills already before the exchange, but he also feels it is important to continue learning the new language in order to get deeper into its culture. His attitude towards the host country seems tolerant and he is open for new experiences: e.g., he doesn’t love the dark winter, but he has been able to find ways to spend meaningful free time by engaging to different activities with his friends

Also, the self-motivation of the student must have helped in the adaptation process, because he didn’t feel the pressure to go to study abroad, but sees it as his own, active choice. He has also found a job for himself:

*I am employed at the Turkish fast-food, *Tori Döner and Burgers*, situated within the newly constructed *Kauppahalli* building, centrally located in Joensuu city. Over the course of my residency in Finland, I have acquired the ability to engage in candid and direct communication with my employer at the workplace.*

The student’s academical goal is to finish his studies in year 2024. Studying in abroad has widened his horizon and brought him not just the language skills but also intercultural competence, which will come into use in the field of international business.

Culturally Oriented Finnish Language Teaching

Ward, Bochner and Furnham (2005, 268) conclude that in order to function effectively in a foreign cultural environment “is to acquire relevant basic social skills through behavioural culture training, mentoring and learning about the historical, philosophical and sociopolitical foundations of the host society”. During the Finnish language classes the students can be prepared for the exchange, not just by improving their language skills but also paying attention on intercultural communicative competence by exploring the habits and customs as well as acquiring knowledge of the policies and history of the host society.

These topics mentioned are the kind, which language teachers naturally tend to include in their teaching. Often also the teaching materials take into account the cultural aspects: when teaching the dates, also the festivals are studied, when learning the past tense, the text can describe the history of Finland or when reading a newspaper article, it describes the current changes in Finnish society.

However, it should be kept in mind, that the cultural information can be included into language classes from the very beginner’s level. For example, when teaching the basic phrases, it can be mentioned, that in Finland shaking hands is very common on official occasions, and also the women shake hands. Also, a teacher can be called by the first name, and when addressing, the second person singular is used. Hence the language level doesn’t need to be high in order to naturally incorporate cultural aspects into teaching.

Also, it is worth to discuss the Finnish communication culture in general, but as well as the tools for communication. It might come as a surprise to the teacher, that e-mail is not necessarily a familiar tool for communication for a student. Thus, the conventions of an e-mail should be included in language teaching.

If a student is planning to study in Finland, according to the interview, it is also important to mention the need for the fluent English skills in English speaking programmes, stress the need for Finnish skills and the basic IT-skills in order to understand the different digital tools and systems used. On a more practical level, the interviewed student urges future exchange students to prepare oneself for hard winter with the warm clothes as well as for studying with a well-functioning computer and a mobile phone.

Ward et al. (2005) mention Hofstede’s research on 1980’s about the person-group relationship, which he states to differ from culture to culture. According to his research, the countries can be classified along four bipolar dimensions, which are the following: individualism/collectivism, power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and Masculinity/Femininity. (Ward et al. 2005, 11-12.)

The interview of an exchange student described in this article shows, that the phenomenon he pays attention on, often include these dimensions. For example, in Finland the power distance between a student and a teacher is narrow, which affects to the communication culture in the class: the teacher doesn’t feel the questions done by students disturbing or inappropriate. Also, the need for personal space in Finland is bigger than many other countries. The feelings of rudeness might be due to the individualistic culture of the Finns: focusing on the self and the immediate family rather than on the community. On the personal experience the writer of the article could also add, that Finnish people, in general, have a low tolerance for uncertainty, and for example, the equality between sexes is in Finland very important. Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that Hofstede’s ideas would be worth to mention to the students, who are planning to

participate into the exchange programmes, in order to deepen their cultural understanding of the culture of the host country.

Conclusion

Many higher-level institutions in Finland offer to international students different kinds of orientation weeks and programmes or cultural courses about the host country. Intercultural competence grows when encountering with different cultures, but the student can increase his/her knowledge of the host country, its’ customs, history and society, as well as his/her language skills, already when still in home country. A natural forum for teaching cultural information are the Finnish language classes, where the cultural themes can be included into language teaching already at the very beginner’s level.

REFERENCES

1. Eze Ogbonna, E. (2015) International Student’s Studying Abroad Challenges: Culture shock?
2. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews* Vol.5 No.1, pp.44 – 51. Retrived from <https://www.ijsshr.com/journal/index.php/IJSSHR/article/view/63/52>
3. Lasonen, J., Halonen, M., Pini Kemppainen, R. & Teräs, M. (2009). Monikulttuurisuus, kulttuurienvälisyys ja osaamisen tunnustamisen tarve. In J. Lasonen & M. Halonen (Eds.), *Kulttuurienväläinen osaaminen koulutuksessa ja työelämässä* (pp. 9-24). FERA – Suomen kasvatustieteellinen seura ry. Kasvatusalan tutkimuksia 43. Jyväskylän yliopistopaino: Jyväskylä. Retrived from https://jyx.jyu.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/84708/978-952-7411-20-9_KT_43_jyx.pdf?
4. University of Helsinki. Culture Shock & Home Sickness. Studies service. Retrived 26.10.2023 from
5. <https://studies.helsinki.fi/instructions/article/culture-shock-homesickness>.
6. Ward, C., Bochner, S. & Furnham, A. (2005). *The Psychology of Culture Shock*. Routledge: London.